

**FOOD, HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH
INFRASTRUCTURES TO TACKLE EMERGING PRIORITIES
(GA n. 101131588)**

**Milestone 3.1 – First catalogue of the current
state of services offered across European RIs**

WP 3 – UU + MU

Introduction

A questionnaire was distributed to relevant European RIs and organizations to identify potential service domains and to gather the details on the core methodologies offered at each site. The collected data covers services relevant across the broad spectrum of specific parameters (physical, chemical, in vitro, in vivo biological properties) allowing researchers to address challenges relevant to health, food, and environmental conditions and the overall impact of artificial materials on health. As a consequence, services will encompass several scales, from the molecular level all the way to ecosystems. This is presented in this **catalogue of the current state of services offered across European RI**.

Participant data

Date of current version: 30-01-2025

Number of participants: 64

It was first assessed if the facility is involved in a European or national project on “artificial materials”, and if these then impact on the research domains defined in the plot below. Participants could reply with Yes, Maybe or No:

More specifically, a total number of 37 facilities belong to an ESFRI project or landmark, and 18 participants were unaware if their facility belongs to one. The other 9 facilities indicated to not belong to such projects or landmark. The distribution of indicated ESFRI projects or landmarks is represented below:

The ESFRIs BBMRI ERIC, EATRIS ERIC, ECRIN ERIC, EMPHASIS, ERINHA, EU-IBISBA, EU-OPENSUREN ERIC and INFRAFRONTIER were not represented.

Services

The participants were asked to fill in current services they provide on artificial (micro- and nano) materials, or to consider if they may have the capacity to offer them. The following categorized services are available:

The majority of services is focusing on the physical / chemical or structural characterization of micro- and nanoparticles and/or plastics. The impact is represented in e.g. the toxicity of MNPs, the exposure assessment of MNPs or the biological activity of MNPs. The participants were asked to link their services to impact: on what topics do the services have impact? This is highlighted in the following chart.

Specific categories of techniques are monitored as service to map the research infrastructure for artificial materials. These are:

- X-ray techniques
- Magnetic techniques
- OMICS techniques
- Optical spectroscopic techniques
- Light scattering techniques
- Microscopy techniques
- Mass spectrometry techniques
- Biological studies
- Data and Bioinformatic methodologies

Above are the services provided by the participants in absolute numbers, for which the service is counted when it is either already available or planned to be available in two years. The majority of services is centered on micro-spectroscopic techniques on the analytical side, and biological studies on the impact side, whereas X-ray and magnetic technologies are lowest in number. Specific measurement techniques are provided per category, which are shown below together with the amount of facilities providing them. If these facilities belong to an ESFRI, this is specified (only if already present, not when planned).

● Yes, have technique / method ● Plan to have (in 2 years) ● Has the potential to include ● Not applicable / None

OMICS

Optical spectroscopy

Light-scattering

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● Yes, have technique / method ● Plan to have (in 2 years) ● Has the potential to include ● Not applicable / None

Microscopy

Mass spectrometry

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The above analysis provides insights into the services available as indicated by all participants, as well as by the ESFRIs represented. The majority of services is available and well represented over the ESFRIs, although X-Ray, scattering and certain microscopy techniques seem to be under-represented. This catalogue additionally serves as a tool to indicate the existing gaps within the research landscape both related and unrelated to the ESFRIs on artificial materials.

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